

RULE-BASED ACCOUNTING: THE UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES OF

WARRANT LIABILITIES

by

James E. Salski

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2992-6504

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Approved by:

Date:

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Dr. Hung-Yuan Lu, Associate Director, School of Accountancy

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Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES OF WARRANT LIABILITIES

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
<i>AICPA</i>	American Institute of Certified Public Accountants
<i>ANOVA</i>	Analysis of variance
<i>APIC</i>	Additional paid-in capital
<i>ASC</i>	Accounting Standards Codification [®]
<i>BV</i>	Book value
<i>dF</i>	Degree of freedom
<i>EPS</i>	Earnings per share
<i>F</i>	F statistic
<i>FASB</i>	Financial Accounting Standards Board
<i>FV</i>	Fair value
<i>GAAP</i>	(U.S.) Generally Accepted Accounting Principles
<i>IPO</i>	Initial public offering
<i>MS</i>	Mean squares
<i>MV</i>	Market value
<i>NI</i>	Net income
<i>NYSE</i>	New York Stock Exchange
<i>OCA</i>	Office of the Chief Accountant
<i>OI</i>	Operating income
<i>PCAOB</i>	Public Company Accounting Oversight Board
<i>R</i>	Correlation coefficient
<i>SEC</i>	U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission
<i>SPAC</i>	Special-purpose acquisition company
<i>SS</i>	Sum of squares

Rule-Based Accounting: The Unintended Consequences of Warrant Liabilities**By James E. Salski****Abstract**

The surge of special-purpose acquisition companies (SPACs) provided an attainable way for startups to raise capital, however, it also exposed the unintended consequences of rule-based accounting in accordance with U.S. Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP). Upon initial public offering (IPO), along with common shares, SPACs issue warrants that permit and encourage investors to acquire additional shares at a fixed, intended lower price, independent of market valuation. The warrant's book value is therefore not equal to market value of the share, which fails the equity test under ASC 815 pronouncement, thus forcing an entity to classify such warrants as liabilities. The warrants' fair value dramatically counters the SPAC's equity accounts, including revenue, leading to diminished earnings per share (EPS), and yielding reduced GAAP-compliant profit, which may mislead prosperous and existing shareholders as well as existing warrant holders who shun from investing upon detecting the grandiose liability. A case study of a SPAC-born entity, Butterfly, Inc., offers invaluable insight on how warrant liabilities corrupt operating income and discourage share acquisition. To circumvent improper diagnosis, retail investors may choose to compute additional ratios and set benchmarks such as pro forma operating income and EPS to determine a SPAC's investment merit.

Problem Statement and Research Questions

The popularization of special-purpose acquisition companies (SPACs) disturbed the traditional initial public offering (IPO) process and the associated accounting practices. With the new method, a company records its warrants (investors' rights for additional stock acquisition) as liabilities at fair value (FV) rather than as equity, which results in a gross underrepresentation of its actual income or loss. This treatment exposed financial statement presentation limitations of the current U.S. Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP).

The U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) defines a SPAC, also called a “blank check” company, as “a special purpose acquisition vehicle [...] is a company that has no commercial operations and is formed solely to raise capital so it can acquire a private operating company and take that private company public” (Crenshaw), meaning, the sole purpose of a SPAC is to find a prospective company to merge with via a de-SPAC transaction, thus taking the company public.

With the recent “SPAC boom”, countless companies chose SPACs as their preferred way towards an IPO. As Shuli Ren of Bloomberg Opinion writes:

SPACs [...] are one of Wall Street's [most attractive] products. These publicly traded shell companies give tycoons and celebrities the capital to search for splashy one-shot deals [...] [and] they give ordinary investors a way to participate

in the purchase of a hot company before it goes public-a perk usually reserved for the wealthy (Ren).

The warrant liabilities cause issues of valuation and presentation:

- The skewed and considerably increased balance of liabilities caused by the warrants reduces the company's book value (BV) (value assessed purely from the GAAP-compliant balance sheet which does not equal the entity's value on the stock market, i.e., market capitalization).
- The additional liabilities curtail the entity's net income on financial statements regardless of their actual performance which leads to decreased clarity on a reported form and may be convoluting for inexperienced retail investors.

Often, owners chose the SPAC route of IPO unaware of those financial statement consequences of the warrants' classification which may lead to lost stock revenue as potential shareholders shun away from investing, put away by the grandiose liability.

With the investors' increased excitement to invest and with more companies choosing that route, the limitations of the U.S. accounting code are more conspicuous than ever.

Research Questions

Naturally, with such great discrepancies, it is important to examine how do warrant liabilities affect SPACs' financial reporting.

Additionally, it is worth exploring the following detail questions:

- Can the statements of a company's financial position be presented in an alternative way as to separate changes in FV of warrant liabilities from net comprehensive income (loss)?
- Can and should warrant liabilities be excluded from earnings per share (EPS) calculation?
- If not, how can a company and its regulating bodies better inform investors on how to interpret warrant liabilities?

Research Aims and Objectives

The purpose of this study is to identify the unintended consequences of the current U.S. GAAP pertaining to the accounting treatment and financial statement presentation of warrant liabilities and to propose and offer solutions for governing bodies and reporting entities on how to treat and present warrant liabilities in a more lucid way to ensure higher investor literacy and a more accurate valuation of a reporting entity in its filings.

SPAC Lifecycle and its Financial Instruments

SPACs are allowed to bypass the traditional lengthy and expensive IPO process. As SPACs issue their own shares upon SPAC IPO, their owners have a quick way of accumulating funds to merge with the target company. Their shares are sold at \$10 and consist of a founder stock share and a private warrant.

The development cycle of a SPAC can be described in four distinct stages:

1. **Pre-IPO** – Establishment and funding from the founding investors in return for lucrative founder shares (Class B, nonvoting) to be issued at IPO. The sponsors typically pay \$25,000 in exchange for 20% of the total shares outstanding.
2. **IPO** – The remaining 80% of the shares (Class A) are offered as publicly traded units at (typically) \$10 with detachable warrants with an execution (strike) price of \$11.50 allowing investors to purchase additional shares at a fixed price regardless of FV. The warrants may generally be executed 30 days after the IPO or the *post-merger* (CFI) and within 5 years. The IPO itself is conducted via an investment bank, such as Goldman Sachs, Morgan Stanley, etc., who charges a fixed fee, generally 10% of the IPO proceeds (CFI).
3. **Pre-merger** – The accumulated capital from the IPO earns interest as the SPAC searches for the company to merge with. The moment an attractive target is found may also signify an additional influx of capital as investors excited to harvest the possible future monetary benefits of the merger invest additional funds. A SPAC may also not find a target company to merge within the specified time (18-24 months since the IPO) and all the funds must be returned to investors.
4. **Post-merger** – Signified by the de-SPAC transaction. Upon the de-SPAC, the company functions as a regular market-listed publicly traded company.

Per Accounting Standards Codification (ASC) topic 946, the FV valuation method of warrants allocates the price of a SPAC IPO share unit which consists of:

- *A class B share.* The sale of these shares funds the initial costs of establishing a SPAC and the IPO, such as the 2% underwriting fee. These “founder” shares are purchased by the sponsor with the agreement to maintain 20% of the SPACs equity. Reminiscent of a preemptive right, in this case the founders may need to purchase additional shares or forfeit currently held ones to maintain their 20% ratio of ownership. Class B shares are automatically converted into class A shares upon de-SPAC transaction. These shares are to be classified as equity.
- *A private warrant separately available at \$1.50 per warrant with an \$11.50 strike price.* These allow the shareholder to purchase class A stock upon de-SPAC at \$11.50 per share regardless of the common stock’s market price. These warrants are not mandatorily redeemable; therefore, they are classified as equity under ASC 718 (subject to discussion in part *Warrant Classification* [p. 23])

Upon the IPO, the SPAC issues publicly available units at \$10 each containing:

- *A Class A share.* Compared to Class B, Class A shares *generally* have more voting rights in the unpredictable market.
- *Public warrant with an \$11.50 strike price.* The warrants allow a holder to acquire *additional* Class A shares at a fixed price of \$11.50 regardless of the market price. Suppose the shares’ price in the market is \$15. A warrant holder, by purchasing an additional share at \$11.50, will take advantage of a relative discount of \$3.50. If the shares are available in the market at a price lower than the warrant’s strike, say \$10, then a warrant holder will choose not to exercise the

warrant and possibly purchase additional shares directly as in the case of the shares being available at \$10, he or she would be effectively losing \$1.50 per share by exercising the \$11.50 warrant (net of any applicable brokerage fees). The warrants exercise price must be settled in cash. If the strike price is above MV (above \$18) after 30 trading days upon expiration and usually entitled to a small compensation, usually \$0.01 per warrant if not exercised. Per FINRA's sample provision:

Any Public Warrants that remain unexercised following 5:00 p.m. New York City time on the Redemption Date will be void and no longer exercisable, and the holders of those Public Warrants will be entitled to receive only the redemption price of \$0.01 per warrant (FINRA).

Other provisions allow to redeem the expired warrants at \$0.10 per, or to redeem for stock on a make-whole, cashless basis, using a table if the shares trade above \$10 but at less than \$18, when the company would be obligated to pay \$0.01 per warrant. The number of shares received using such table will be less than the number received via warrant exercise, however, it serves as compensation for the shareholder's time and patience.

SPAC Warrants

Compared to how warrants of traditional IPO route entities are treated by GAAP as equity, in the case of a SPAC IPO, the warrants shall be classified as liabilities.

The FASB defines *assets* as “probable future economic benefits obtained or controlled by a particular entity as a result of past transactions or events” (FASB).

The FASB defines *liabilities* as follows:

Liabilities are probable future sacrifices of economic benefits arising from present obligations of a particular entity to transfer assets or provide services to other entities in the future as a result of past transactions or events (FASB).

Equity is defined as the leftover interest (ownership) in the company’s assets after deducting the liabilities (FASB). This is further outlined in ASC 480.

From the highest level, the fundamental accounting equation entails, assets must equal to the sum of liabilities and equity.

Per FASB, the warrants issued by SPACs at founding (pre-IPO) are to be classified as equity, whereas shares issued at IPO must be classified as liabilities. The warrants classified as liabilities are the focus of the study.

Per SPAC guidelines, the total selling price of an IPO unit (one Class A share and one public warrant with a strike price of \$11.50) is \$10. Upon share sale, the dollar amounts allocated towards stock (and paid-in capital) do not change. Per *figure 1*, at the point the class A’s share price increases above \$11.50 (the warrant strike price), the SPAC must classify the difference (shortfall) of the strike as a liability.

In the illustration, it is assumed that a fictitious example company went public via a SPAC IPO (pre-merger) and issued the standard share package for \$10 each. At the point

its share price surpassed \$11.50, in the illustration's case, reached \$15, the company had to record a liability of \$3.50 per share. Once the stock price increased to \$20, the liability balance had to be increased to \$8.50. The \$5 increase in share price amounted to a \$5 increase in the balance of the warrant liability. Though the incremental changes are of the same incremental monetary value, as seen in the table below, a stock price increase of 33% (from \$15 to \$20) resulted in a 143% increase in the balance of warrant liabilities. Though in unit share transactions these changes may seem miniscule, on a company-wide level, where the number of shares outstanding may near or exceed 200 million (as in the case of the company analyzed in the study), the change in the FV of warrant liabilities may be vast and have grandiose consequences on a firm's reported financial position.

The company does not benefit from the increased price of its shares; however, it loses net income by recording a liability proportionate to that increase.

Figure 1:

Warrant liability FV changes demonstration						
	Stock price	Warrant strike price	Warrant FV	Stock price % change	Warrant FV % change	Warrant FV as % of Stock price
At issuance	\$ 10.00	\$ 11.50	\$ -			
Price decrease scenario	\$ 5.00	11.50	\$ -	-50%	-	-
	15.00	11.50	3.50	200%	-	23%
Price Increase scenarios	20.00	11.50	8.50	33%	143%	43%
	80.00	11.50	68.50	300%	706%	86%
	50.00	11.50	38.50	-38%	-44%	77%
	100.00	11.50	88.50	25%	29%	89%

The changes are more easily visible in this graph quantifying *approximate* changes of a warrant's FV as stock price varies from \$1 to \$30 assuming no redemptions:

Figure 2:

It is important to notice that, on the graph, the distance between the *Stock price* and the *Warrant FV* will always be the warrant's strike price (\$11.50), which means that the total balance in the warrant liability account would be the total market value *less* the number of warrants outstanding multiplied by the strike price.

Therefore:

Stock price increases → Warrant FV increases → Understated NI (and EPS).

Stock price decreases → Warrant FV decreases → Overstated NI (and EPS).

Such a disconnect between GAAP-compliant reporting and an entity’s actual financial performance is very evident in the case of Butterfly Network, Inc. (NYSE: BFLY) (“Butterfly” or “Company”), a “digital health business transforming care with hand-held, whole body ultrasound [devices]” (Butterfly), that came to existence via a de-SPAC transaction.

In the case of Butterfly, the treatment results in inflating net operating income (OI), net income (NI), and EPS by as much as thousands of percent.

Figure 7 (Excerpt):

	12/31/2020	Three months ended		
		3/31/2021	6/30/2021	9/30/2021
Reporting entity	Butterfly	Butterfly	Butterfly	Butterfly
Income (loss) from operations	(3,190,991.00)	(53,748,000.00)	(36,687,000.00)	(56,987,000.00)
Warrant liabilities	-	133,214,000.00	99,754,000.00	56,796,000.00
Change in FV of warrant liabilities	(128,463,731.00)	(54,112,000.00)	(33,458,000.00)	(42,958,000.00)
Change in FV of warrant liabilities as % of operating income (loss)	4026%	101%	91%	75%
Net comprehensive income (loss)	(131,814,633.00)	(690,000.00)	(2,942,000.00)	(13,561,000.00)

Source: Butterfly, SEC

Methodology

With thousands of publicly traded companies available to buy into in the U.S., choosing the most adequate shares (or combination thereof) requires meticulous analysis, often from finance professionals and brokerages. Companies report the statements of their financial positions to the SEC, which is responsible for 1) protecting investors, 2) maintaining fair, orderly, and efficient markets, and 3) facilitating capital formation (SEC). These reports are publicly available to all on the SEC's website – www.sec.gov.

The reports include but are not limited to:

- 10-K – Audited annual report. The most meticulous and the most regulated filing.
- 10-Q – Unaudited quarterly report.
- 8-K – Unaudited current report, issued to announce major events that shareholders should be informed of.

As the only filing legally required to be audited by an independent Certified Public Accountant (CPA) firm (firm not otherwise affiliated with or engaged in the preparation or evaluation of the client firm's operations), Form10-K serves as the most reliable source of information for investors. Subsequently listed forms may serve as complements with additional indicators useful before the succeeding annual Form10-K is issued. A later part of the thesis will analyze a sample company's Form10-K to answer the later research questions.

These reports will be analyzed in conjunction with official regulating and governing bodies' publications and guidelines, such as those of American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA), FASB, in the context of U.S. GAAP, Public Company Accounting Oversight Board (PCAOB), and SEC.

This study will analyze and quantify the financial reports of a sample entity that stemmed from a de-SPAC transaction – Butterfly Network, Inc (NYSE: BFLY). The methods used in the analysis include but are not limited to:

- Statistical analyses.
- Regression analyses.
- Archival stock price and volume analyses.
- Visual data analytics.

Background

Capital and the Share System

The major constraint in most businesses' objective of expansion is the difficulty of obtaining proper funding. The most attractive way of financing expansion for many entities is via issuing stock, that is, heavily diluted publicly available shares of ownership that private individuals may purchase in hopes of increasing the value of their holdings as the business grows.

Stock issuance and IPO track are amenities available to corporations, that is, legal entities

And this number has been rising rapidly in recent years:

Figure 3:

Source: Statista

These shares are defined by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), an accounting standard-setting body within the United States, in ASC 480 as such:

Shares includes various forms of ownership that may not take the legal form of securities (for example, partnership interests), as well as other interests, including those that are liabilities in substance but not in form. (Business entities have interest holders that are commonly known by specialized names, such as

stockholders, partners, and proprietors, and by more general names, such as investors, but all are encompassed by the descriptive term owners. Equity or business entities is, thus, commonly known by several names, such as owners' equity, stockholders' equity, ownership, equity capital, partners' capital, and proprietorship. Some entities [for example, mutual organizations] do not have stockholders, partners, or proprietors in the usual sense of those terms but do have participants whose interests are essentially ownership interests, residual interests, or both) (FASB, 2022).

This means that by buying a share, the shareholder lends their money to the company in return for interests in its business while assuming risk limited to the amount spent for the shares. Owning shares gives the shareholder certain rights:

- To proportionally share voting power on major issues.
- To proportionally own a portion of the company.
- To transfer ownership of the owned proportion of the company.
- To proportionally share in profits (losses) and be entitled to distributions via a dividend.
- To be able to inspect corporate records.
- To have the right to a lawsuit for unjust acts.
- To retain their proportional ownership of company shares via the preemptive right.

The two most common kinds of shares are common shares and preferred shares.

Common shares prioritize voting rights, that is, decision making about the entity's future.

Common shareholders, however, are last in line when it comes to profit distribution.

Preferred shares, on the other hand, do not give the shareholder voting rights, yet guarantee preference (thus preferred stock) when it comes to profit distribution via a dividend. Such shares are available to everyone of legal age and the acquisition process may take just seconds with popular brokerage mobile apps, which makes the process so much more convenient for investors, and capital more available than ever for entities.

SPAC Initial Public Offering

To issue stock, a company must first become a public corporate structure via the initial public offering (IPO). This is a lengthy and expensive method that involves external audits and consultancies.

This process has been greatly accelerated with SPACs which, as mentioned before, need no operations and, in most cases, files its IPO long before the target company for the merger is found, which allows it to collect capital before carrying the burden of performing for the shareholders.

The method's increased popularity is greatly visible when the number of IPOs in the U.S.

(*figure 4*) is conjugated with the number of SPAC IPOs:

Figure 4:

Source: Statista

In 2021, SPAC IPOs constituted 64% of all U.S. IPOs (613 SPAC IPOs out of total 951 IPOs in the U.S. that year). This growth also comes with record-breaking levels of capital. Year 2020 saw a record \$83 billion raised in capital (Ren). 2021 saw numbers of \$162 billion which shows growth of 195% year to year (Statista). Additionally, on IPO, SPACs can earn more than 20,000% of the funds initially provided by sponsors (SPAC Consultants).

Notably, most of this capital does not come from venture capitalists, banks, or finance professionals. Ren notes that “[individual investors] account for about 40% of SPAC trading on [Bank of America] Securities Inc.'s trading platforms. This year [2021], SPACs on average are rising more than 6% on their first day of trading, up from last year's 1.6%, a sign of heavy retail participation” (Ren). This presents the question of the investing and SPAC knowledge of such investor.

Review of Accounting Guidelines

The FASB mandates how instruments should be valued and classified on financial documents. The Accounting Standards Codification (ASC) is issued by FASB and “is the single source of authoritative nongovernmental U.S. generally accepted accounting principles (US GAAP). The Codification is effective for interim and annual periods ending after September 15, 2009. All other accounting literature not included in the Codification is nonauthoritative.” (FASB).

The following ASC sections offer guidelines are relevant in determining a warrant’s classification as a liability or equity.

Fair Value Measurement

The measurement of value at which a SPAC is required to report is warrant liabilities is the fair value method, the details of which are contained in ASC 946:

ASC 946 Financial Services – Investment Companies

The code describes fair value (FV) in its barest as “the price that would be received to sell an asset or paid to transfer a liability in an orderly transaction¹ between market participants at the measurement date” (FASB), meaning, the FV method acts as a measure of an instrument’s monetary value in the market. The market value (MV) does not have to be equal to the fair value, and it almost never is. A company shares are available on the market at a total price (market value) higher than the entity’s book value (price to book value) if the investors are assured of its’ high-yielding future performance (picture the 2000s dot-com bubble, or current tech giants, such as Alphabet [\$GOOGL]). Contrariwise, when investors are not compelled to buy or hold a company’s shares because of its opaque future concerns, the price to book value will be less than 1 (such as Air Lease (\$AL), an aircraft leasing company troubled by the post Covid-19 pandemic slowdown in air travel) (Bloomberg), though there are other factors that affect the price of the share beyond the scope of this thesis.

Subtopic 10-55-23 “an investor in an investment company contributes funds to acquire ownership interests [shares at MV], and the value of those interests is dependent on the changes in the fair value of the underlying investments of the investment company” (FASB). This elaborates on the issue that the price paid for the security in the market is

¹ A transaction that assumes exposure to the market for a period before the measurement date to allow for marketing activities that are usual and customary for transactions involving such assets or liabilities; it is not a forced transaction (for example, a forced liquidation or distress sale) (FASB).

the MV, whereas the definite value, FV, of the security, is determined by the company's balance sheet.

Furthermore, per subtopic 20-25-7:

Accounting for shareholder transactions of open-end funds differs from the accounting followed by commercial entities in several key aspects. Sales of fund shares are recorded daily by crediting capital stock for the par value of the stock to be issued and additional paid-in capital for the amount paid over the par value; redemptions are recorded daily by debiting those accounts. The offsetting debit (credit), however, is made to an asset (liability) account, typically captioned as receivable for fund shares sold (payable for fund shares redeemed). These entries are made on or as of the date the order to purchase or sell fund shares is received (trade date), not on the day the payment is due (settlement date) as is typical practice for the recording of issuance of equity shares by commercial entities (FASB).

As a SPAC exposes shareholders to gains and losses (unrealized granted the shareholder does not sell shares) as the MV and the FV of the warrants fluctuate. A company will record the cash received (MV) and allocate the excess of its par value (a non-value-related nominal dollar amount assigned to a stock share by a corporation's charter) to additional paid-in capital (APIC). Since the MV becomes the BV, the value of the stock on an entity's balance sheet will become unchanged, yet the redemption value of a share by exercising warrants will change depending on the MV of the shares, recalling:

Stock price increases → Warrant FV increases → Understated NI (and EPS);

Stock price decreases → Warrant FV decreases → Overstated NI (and EPS).

A company will therefore increase the balance of the warrant account shall the stock MV increase, and vice versa.

Warrant Classification

The following ASC sections offer guidance pertaining to the accounting treatment and classification of instruments as liabilities or equity. The careful analysis and synthesis of the sections will allow to construct a decision tree which will make it possible to accurately classify warrants and other instruments. The following steps are adapted from Ernst and Young's Technical Line - Navigating the requirements for merging with a special purpose acquisition company.

ASC 718 Compensation – Stock Compensation

This standard discusses the balance sheet classification of share-based remuneration and payments including, but not limited to, employee stock ownership plans and employee stock purchase plans (FASB). Often, merger target's officers will negotiate compensation in the form of additional shares (or instruments) paid out proportionally with the SPAC's financial performance. These might be offered by the SPAC eagerly as a form of embellishing the blank-check and attracting the target to committing to the merger if they would not without the additional perk. These build additional value for the stakeholders

(including employees). These contingent additional shares-to-be are referred to as contingent payments, and more precisely, as *earnout agreements* and are to be classified at FV as warrants.

Per Forbes:

An “earnout” is a contractual mechanism in a merger or acquisition agreement, which provides for contingent additional payments from a buyer of a company to the seller’s shareholders. Earnouts are typically “earned” if the business acquired meets certain financial or other milestones after the acquisition is closed.

An earnout can be useful if the parties are having difficulty reaching agreement on an upfront cash price, with the earnout as a way of bridging the different views on valuation of the buyer and seller (Forbes).

The target recipients of those earnout shares are the employees-to-be of the legal entity to be formed upon the de-SPAC transaction, in other words, the current employees of the company the SPAC is interested in merging with. With an earnout, a founder share will have a fixed component, which will be the initial class B share with its respective private warrant, and the variable, performance-based component will be an additional number (or fraction) of warrants dependent on the future financial performance. As a free-standing, detachable agreement offered as compensation for the acquisition, and paid out as form of enticement to close the financing deal to the company’s employees, the units are subject to consideration under ASC 718.

The objectives of the standard 718 are listed in the subtopic 10-10-1:

The objective of accounting for transactions under share-based payment arrangements is to recognize in the financial statements the goods or services received in exchange for equity instruments granted or liabilities incurred and the related cost to the entity as those goods or services are received (FASB).

Subtopic 10-10-2 further discusses the value measurements of such warrants:

This Topic requires that the cost resulting from all share-based payment transactions be recognized in the financial statements. This Topic establishes fair value as the measurement objective in accounting for share-based payment arrangements and requires all entities to apply a fair-value-based measurement method in accounting for share-based payment transactions except for equity instruments held by employee stock ownership plans (FASB).

As the earnout warrants are redeemable for shares and are provided to the merger target's employees as payment, though non-cash, shall be recorded in the company's financials at FV. Subtopic 10-15-4 notes that:

Share-based payments awarded to a grantee by a related party or other holder of an economic interest in the entity as compensation for goods or services provided to the reporting entity are share-based payment transactions to be accounted for under this Topic unless the transfer is clearly for a purpose other than compensation for goods or services to the reporting entity. The substance of such

a transaction is that the economic interest holder makes a capital contribution to the reporting entity, and that entity makes a share-based payment to the grantee in exchange for services rendered or goods received. An example of a situation in which such a transfer is not compensation is a transfer to settle an obligation of the economic interest holder to the grantee that is unrelated to goods or services to be used or consumed in a grantor's own operations (FASB).

The good or service in return for which the earnout warrants are issued is the merger target company itself. Employees, and therefore, stakeholders, would be the one receiving such shares to gain further voting support for the merger.

The question to be asked while evaluating a warrant in scope of ASC 718 is:

Is the warrant a free-standing instrument provided to the employee as compensation?

If the answer is **yes**, then the warrant shall be classified as equity, subject to allocation adjustments to FV. These warrants, classified as equity, do not pose the risk of altering net income and therefore affecting EPS to any extent, therefore, they are not relevant to the forthcoming discussion. If the answer is **no**, then the instrument shall be further analyzed in scope of ASC 480.

Earn-out arrangements that do not meet the ASC 718 benchmarks, meaning, were not paid out as compensation, are to be classified as equity, shall be evaluated under ASC 815-40 (discussed in a later part of the section).

Furthermore, earnout warrants are not mandatorily redeemable, therefore a person who overlooked the guidelines of ASC 718 but followed the suggested next evaluation (ASC 480), would still arrive at the same conclusion.

ASC 480 – Distinguishing Liabilities from Equity

Warrants may have qualities of both liabilities and equity, in the meaning that, like liabilities, they represent the issuer's obligation to exchange such warrant for a number of shares, and, like equity, they indicate ownership of assets. ASC 480 offers guidelines as to how separate and classify such instruments in a binary meaning.

The general examples for distinguishing an instrument as a liability are the following outlines in subtopic 10-05-2:

- a. An entity incurs a conditional obligation to transfer assets by issuing (writing) a put option that would, if exercised, require the entity to repurchase its equity shares by physical settlement. (Further, an instrument that requires the issuer to settle its obligation by issuing another instrument [for example, a note payable in cash] ultimately requires settlement by a transfer of assets.)
- b. An entity incurs a conditional obligation to transfer assets by issuing a similar contract that requires or could require net cash settlement.
- c. An entity incurs a conditional obligation to issue its equity shares by issuing a similar contract that requires net share settlement (FASB).

In the case of warrants issued as a result of founder shares, they are not mandatorily converted into Class A shares upon SPAC IPO, therefore do not meet the ASC 480 guidelines for classification as liabilities.

The additional share packages with an included public warrant purchased at the IPO by either initial investors (as their entitlement to fulfill the preemptive right), funds, or first-time retail investors, are redeemable into additional Class A shares, usually within 30 days after the IPO for 5 years (\$10 or more 30 market days after the redemption date will yield \$0.01 per warrant. If the MV of shares is equal to or more than \$18, the amount paid out per warrant will be \$0.01). This can be either done via a \$0.01 or \$0.10 redemption, meaning warrant holders receive \$0.01 or \$0.10 per expired warrant if they chose not to exercise. They may also choose to receive shares using a make-whole table if the MV of shares is above \$18 (EY).

Furthermore, subtopic 10-25-8 instructs that:

An entity shall classify as a liability (or an asset in some circumstances) any financial instrument, other than an outstanding share, that, at inception, has both of the following characteristics:

- a. It embodies an obligation to repurchase the issuer's equity shares, or is indexed to such an obligation.
- b. It requires or may require the issuer to settle the obligation by transferring assets (FASB).

ASC 946 previously discussed the fair value approach at assigning value to securities.

ASC 480-10-55-25 further outlines the approach for liabilities and labels them as

derivatives (to be further discussed in ASC 815):

[...] the monetary value of the obligation would be predominantly based on variations in something other than the fair value of the issuer's (guarantor's) equity shares and, therefore, the obligation would be classified as a liability under paragraph 480-10-25-14(b). That obligation differs in degree from the obligation under a contract that is indexed in part to the issuer's shares and in part (but not predominantly) to something other than the issuer's shares (commonly called a dual-indexed obligation). The latter contract is not within the scope of this Subtopic. That paragraph applies only if the monetary value of an obligation to issue equity shares is based solely or predominantly on variations in something other than the fair value of the issuer's equity shares. For example, an instrument meeting the definition of a derivative instrument that requires delivery of a variable number of the issuer's equity shares with a monetary value equaling changes in the price of a fixed number of the issuer's shares multiplied by the Euro/U.S. dollar exchange rate embodies an obligation with a monetary value that is based on variations in both the issuer's share price and the foreign exchange rate and, therefore, is not within the scope of this Subtopic. (However, that instrument would be a derivative instrument under Topic 815. Paragraphs 815-10-15-74(a) and 815-10-15-75(b) address derivative instruments that are dual

indexed and require an issuer to report those instruments as derivative instrument liabilities or assets) (FASB).

The questions to ask while evaluating warrants against ASC 480 is:

Are the warrant-holders obligated to buy additional shares and settle the obligation by transferring assets (such as cash)?

If the answer is **yes**, the warrants shall be classified as liabilities under ASC 480. If the answer is **no**, the warrants require further investigation under ASC 815.

ASC 815 – Derivatives and Hedging

The section defines hedged derivatives, which, if the standards are met, can be classified as equity for the purposes of financial reporting. FASB defines derivatives and hedging in subtopic 10-10-1:

Four fundamental decisions serve as cornerstones underlying the guidance in this Topic:

- a. Derivative instruments represent rights or obligations that meet the definitions of assets or liabilities and should be reported in financial statements.
- b. Fair value is the most relevant measure for financial instruments and the only relevant measure for derivative instruments. Derivative instruments should be measured at fair value, and adjustments to the carrying amount

of hedged items should reflect changes in their fair value (that is, gains or losses) that are attributable to the risk being hedged and that arise while the hedge is in effect.

- c. Only items that are assets or liabilities should be reported as such in financial statements.
- d. Special accounting for items designated as being hedged should be provided only for qualifying items. One aspect of qualification should be an assessment of the expectation of effective offsetting changes in fair values or cash flows during the term of the hedge for the risk being hedged (FASB).

In the scope of the warrant liabilities being the focus of the study, the definition of derivative instruments is met by their nature of an obligation to issue or exchange the warrants for additional shares of Class A stock. The definition of a hedged unit is also met, as the warrants are reported at FV, with the allocation subject to the stock price fluctuations. This method is further outlined in the subtopic 10-05-4:

This Topic requires that an entity recognize derivative instruments, including certain derivative instruments embedded in other contracts, as assets or liabilities in the statement of financial position and measure them at fair value. If certain conditions are met, an entity may elect, under this Topic, to designate a derivative instrument in any one of the following ways:

- a. A hedge of the exposure to changes in the fair value of a recognized asset or liability, or of an unrecognized firm commitment, that are attributable to a particular risk (referred to as a fair value hedge)
- b. A hedge of the exposure to variability in the cash flows of a recognized asset or liability, or of a forecasted transaction, that is attributable to a particular risk (referred to as a cash flow hedge)
- c. A hedge of the foreign currency exposure of any one of the following:
 1. An unrecognized firm commitment (a foreign currency fair value hedge)
 2. An available-for-sale debt security (a foreign currency fair value hedge)
 3. A forecasted transaction (a foreign currency cash flow hedge)
 4. A net investment in a foreign operation (FASB).

The SPAC warrants do not meet any of those points, except, potentially, point a. The classification of the warrants shall be further evaluated in scope of topic 815-40 which offers an in-depth guideline on how to determine if an instrument is considered to be indexed to an entity's own stock. This calls for an analysis in scope of subtopic 40-15-7

An entity shall evaluate whether an equity-linked financial instrument (or embedded feature), as discussed in paragraphs 815-40-15-5 through 15-8 is considered indexed to its own stock within the meaning of this Subtopic and paragraph 815-10-15-74(a) using the following two-step approach:

- a. Evaluate the instrument's contingent exercise provisions, if any.
- b. Evaluate the instrument's settlement provisions (FASB).

Furthermore, subtopic 40-15-7A outlines that:

An exercise contingency shall not preclude an instrument (or embedded feature) from being considered indexed to an entity's own stock provided that it is not based on either of the following:

- a. An observable market, other than the market for the issuer's stock (if applicable)
- b. An observable index, other than an index calculated or measured solely by reference to the issuer's own operations (for example, sales revenue of the issuer; earnings before interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortization of the issuer; net income of the issuer; or total equity of the issuer).

If the evaluation of Step 1 (this paragraph does not preclude an instrument from being considered indexed to the entity's own stock, the analysis shall proceed to Step 2 (FASB).

An illustration provided by the FASB in subtopic 40-55-26 is helpful in placing the guidelines in context of SPAC warrants:

Entity A issues warrants that permit the holder to buy 100 shares of its common stock for \$10 per share. The warrants have 10-year terms; however, they only

become exercisable if Entity A completes an initial public offering. The warrants are considered indexed to Entity A's own stock based on the following evaluation:

- a. Step 1. The exercise contingency (that is, the initial public offering) is not an observable market or an observable index, so the evaluation of Step 1 does not preclude the warrants from being considered indexed to the entity's own stock. Proceed to Step 2.
- b. Upon exercise, the settlement amount would equal the difference between the fair value of a fixed number of the entity's equity shares (100 shares) and a fixed strike price (\$10 per share) (FASB).

Though SPAC warrants *may* be considered indexed per the illustration as their value is both attributable to an observable index (share price), however, the aforementioned changes in the strike price may preclude it from being classified as indexed. As mentioned in the *SPAC Warrants* (p. 8) section:

The warrants exercise price must be settled in cash. If the strike price is above MV (above \$18) after 30 trading days upon expiration and usually entitled to a small compensation, usually \$0.01 per warrant if not exercised. Other provisions allow to redeem the expired warrants at \$0.10 per, or to redeem for stock on a make-whole, cashless basis, using a table if the shares trade above \$10 but at less than \$18, when the company would be obligated to pay \$0.01 per warrant. This means that investors who do not exercise the warrant, lose

the right to additional stock purchase via the warrant. Per FINRA, such warrant holders are still entitled for compensation of \$0.01 per warrant.

This provision arises a question: if the SPAC can adjust the redemption value of the warrant, is the warrant itself considered indexed? A safe description would be of a 'soft index', where the instrument *generally* is hedged to the stock, however, need be, may be adjusted.

Therefore, the warrants need to be examine whether or not the provisions are fixed, as step .b of subtopic 4-15-7. Subtopic 40-15-7B and C then specify:

815-40-15-7C:

If an instrument's strike price or the number of shares used to calculate the settlement amount would be adjusted upon the occurrence of an exercise contingency, the exercise contingency shall be evaluated under Step 1 (see the preceding paragraph) and the potential adjustment to the instrument's settlement amount shall be evaluated under Step 2 [...] (FASB).

815-40-15-7C:

An instrument (or embedded feature) shall be considered indexed to an entity's own stock if its settlement amount will equal the difference between the following:

- a. The fair value of a fixed number of the entity's equity shares

- b. A fixed monetary amount or a fixed amount of a debt instrument issued by the entity.

For example, an issued share option that gives the counterparty a right to buy a fixed number of the entity's shares for a fixed price or for a fixed stated principal amount of a bond issued by the entity shall be considered indexed to the entity's own stock (FASB).

As the SPAC IPO warrant liability strike prices are not fixed and may be adjusted in contingency, the warrants do not meet the guidelines to be classified as equity and shall be categorized as liabilities.

Furthermore, in an April 12, 2021, statement, the SEC's Office of the Chief Accountant (OCA) released an SEC Staff Statement on Accounting and Reporting Considerations for Warrants Issued by Special Purpose Acquisition Companies outlined:

We [SEC] recently evaluated a fact pattern relating to the terms of warrants that were issued by a SPAC. In this fact pattern, the warrants included provisions that provided for potential changes to the settlement amounts dependent upon the characteristics of the holder of the warrant. Because the holder of the instrument is not an input into the pricing of a fixed-for-fixed option on equity shares, OCA staff concluded that, in this fact pattern, such a provision would preclude the warrants from being indexed to the entity's stock, and thus the warrants should be classified as a liability measured at fair value, with changes in fair value each period reported in earnings (SEC).

The SEC Staff's analysis is consistent with the analysis of ASC 815, and therefore, there are at least questions to ask while evaluating warrants against ASC 815:

Are the warrants indexed to the de-SPAC entity's stock?

If the answer is **no**, further evaluation may be skipped, and the warrants may be comfortably classified as liabilities. If the answer is **yes**, the provision analysis under subtopic 40-25:

[...] unless the economic substance indicates otherwise:

- a. Contracts shall be initially classified as either assets or liabilities in both of the following situations:
 1. Contracts that require net cash settlement (including a requirement to net cash settle the contract if an event occurs and if that event is outside the control of the entity)
 2. Contracts that give the counterparty a choice of net cash settlement or settlement in shares (physical settlement or net share settlement).
- b. Contracts shall be initially classified as equity in both of the following situations:
 1. Contracts that require physical settlement or net share settlement
 2. Contracts that give the entity a choice of net cash settlement or settlement in its own shares (physical settlement or net share settlement), assuming that all the criteria set forth in paragraphs

815-40-25-7 through 25-35 and 815-40-55-2 through 55-6 have been met (FASB).

Then, a question may be asked:

Do the warrants meet equity classification requirements?

If the answer is **yes**, the warrants meet the guidelines for equity. If the answer is **no**, the warrants are to be classified as liabilities.

In the case of SPAC IPO warrants, they shall be classified as liabilities.

Classification Decision Tree

Based on the analyzed ASCs, the following decision tree can be made regarding the classification of financial instruments (adapted from EY).

Figure 5:

Source: Ernst & Young, FASB

SPAC Warrant Classification Decision

The core of the decision to classify such warrants as liabilities are the provisions examined under ASC 815.

The provision used for SPAC shares outlines that in the event of the change of ownership of the shares (and its attached warrants), the warrant holders are entitled to receive cash for the said warrants:

In the event of a tender or exchange offer made to and accepted by holders of more than 50% of the outstanding shares of a single class of common stock, all holders of the warrants would be entitled to receive cash for their warrants. In other words, in the event of a qualifying cash tender offer (which could be outside the control of the entity), all warrant holders would be entitled to cash, while only certain of the holders of the underlying shares of common stock would be entitled to cash (SEC).

This therefore means, that upon change of common stock ownership, shareholders receive compensation, the value of which is outside of the company's control, as is the FV of the warrants. This amount will be share's MV *less* the warrant's strike price (\$11.50). This amount is not in the SPAC's control and GAAP requires it to adjust the liability balance at each reporting date (12/31 for 10-K reports and on the last day of March, June, and September for quarterly 10-Qs). The fluctuations in the share price are

the sole explanation of the warrant liability account balance variations between each reporting period.

Then, per *SPAC Lifecycle and its Financial Instruments* (p. 5):

If the strike price is above MV (above \$18) after 30 trading days upon expiration and usually entitled to a small compensation, usually \$0.01 per warrant if not exercised. Per FINRA's sample provision:

Any Public Warrants that remain unexercised following 5:00 p.m. New York City time on the Redemption Date will be void and no longer exercisable, and the holders of those Public Warrants will be entitled to receive only the redemption price of \$0.01 per warrant (FINRA).

Other provisions allow to redeem the expired warrants at \$0.10 per (if stock MV is more than \$10 but less than \$18), or to redeem for stock on a cashless basis, using a table if the shares trade above \$18 per.

Meaning that, depending on the particular SPAC's provision, the company might need to record a contingent liability of \$0.01 or \$0.10 per warrant shall they not be exercised, or record an additional liability of stock at FV.

To illustrate:

If the shareholder chooses not to exercise warrant due to market conditions, the warrant will expire and the shareholder will receive compensation of either \$0.01 per warrant (since they are not eligible for the \$0.10 payout because of the shares'

MV exceeding \$18) or, since the stock's MV exceeds \$18, elect to receive a number of shares arrived at with the use of a make-whole table. This number of shares is smaller than what would be received shall the warrant holder had exercised the warrant yet serve as a compensation for the time holding it.

The SPAC is inclined to compensate warrant holders who did not sell via a make-whole exchange as it is not losing cash as if the warrant holder sold his or her stake along with the Class A share.

To sum up the classification decision, a SPAC safeguards its warrant holder against any possible monetary loss on redemption, meaning the warrants are not perfectly hedged to the common shares, which constitutes the instrument be classified as a liability.

Case study

The effect of presenting warrants and classifying them as liabilities is most noticeable when presented in scope of a real case. This part of the study will investigate a company that came to existence via a SPAC – Butterfly, Inc (NYSE: BFLY).

Acquired by Longview Acquisition Corp., a SPAC (“Longview” or “SPAC”). Butterfly introduces itself in SEC filings as follows:

The Company, formerly known as Longview Acquisition Corp. (“Longview”), was incorporated in Delaware on February 4, 2020. Prior to February 12, 2021, we were a blank check company formed for the purpose of effecting a merger,

capital stock exchange, asset acquisition, stock purchase, reorganization or similar business combination with one or more businesses.

On February 12, 2021 we completed the business combination (the “Business Combination”) pursuant to the terms of the Business Combination Agreement, dated as of November 19, 2020 (the “Business Combination Agreement”), by and among Longview, Clay Merger Sub, Inc., a Delaware corporation (“Merger Sub”), and Butterfly Network, Inc., a Delaware corporation (“Legacy Butterfly”). The transaction resulted in the Company being renamed to "Butterfly Network, Inc.," Legacy Butterfly being renamed “BFLY Operations, Inc.” and the Company’s Class A common stock and warrants to purchase Class A common stock commencing trading on the New York Stock Exchange ("NYSE") on February 16, 2021 under the symbol "BFLY" and “BFLY WS”, respectively. As a result of the Business Combination, we received gross proceeds of approximately \$589 million and the business of Legacy Butterfly became our business (Butterfly).

The warrant liabilities first appear on the company’s 2020 Form 10-K (amended) for the period ended 12/31/2020. The balance was not present on the 2020 Q3 Form 10-Q, which is consistent with the Class A share MV being below the warrants’ strike price (\$11.50).

The selected balance sheet data is as follows:

Figure 6:

BUTTERFLY NETWORK, INC. (f/k/a LONGVIEW ACQUISITION CORP.)
CONSOLIDATED STATEMENT OF OPERATIONS
FOR THE PERIOD FROM FEBRUARY 4, 2020 (INCEPTION) THROUGH DECEMBER 31, 2020
(As Restated)

Formation and operational costs	\$ 3,774,125
Loss from operations	(3,774,125)
Other income/ (expense):	
Change in fair value of warrants	(128,463,731)
Transaction costs allocated to warrant liability	(286,189)
Interest earned on marketable securities held in Trust Account	355,909
Loss before provision for income taxes	(132,168,136)
Provision for income taxes	(36,632)
Net loss	\$ (132,204,768)
Weighted average shares outstanding of Class A redeemable common stock	40,948,182.0
Basic and diluted income per share, Class A redeemable common stock	\$ —

Source: *Butterfly, SEC*

(The overall differences throughout reporting periods are quantified in *figure 7* in the **Figures** section).

Butterfly, though first records such liabilities on its 2020 Form 10-K, first defines its warrant liabilities in the 2021 Form 10-K. The footnote is as follows:

The valuation of our warrants could increase the volatility in our net income (loss) in our consolidated statements of operations.

The change in fair value of our warrants is the result of changes in stock price and warrants outstanding at each reporting period. The change in fair value of warrant liabilities represents the mark-to-market fair value adjustments to the outstanding warrants issued in connection with the initial public offering of Longview.

Significant changes in our stock price or number of warrants outstanding may adversely affect our net income (loss) in our consolidated statements of operations.

[...] The Company on the date of Closing [12/31/2021] used proceeds of the [business combination] Transactions to pay off \$30.9 million, representing all significant liabilities of the acquiree excluding the warrant liability. **As of the date of the Closing, the Company recorded net liabilities of \$186.5 million with a corresponding offset to additional paid-in capital. The net liabilities include warrant liabilities of \$187.3 million and other insignificant assets and liabilities.** The Company received proceeds of \$0.6 million related to other transactions that occurred at the same time as the Business Combination (Butterfly).

In this footnote, Butterfly warns investors about the volatility of the warrant liability account and its effect on net income (loss) as explained earlier in the study. The grave

impact of such warrants is obvious. The following figure excerpt represents Butterfly's changes in the warrant liability account balance and its net income.

Figure 7 (excerpt):

	Three months ended						
	12/31/2020	3/31/2021	6/30/2021	9/30/2021	12/31/2021	3/31/2022	6/30/2022
Income (loss) from operations	(3.2M)	(53.7M)	(36.7M)	(57M)	(45.3M)	(49.5M)	(48.5M)
Warrant liabilities	-	133.2M	998M	57M	26.2M	21.1M	8.2M
Change in FV of warrant liabilities	(128.5M)	(54.1M)	(335M)	(43M)	(30.6M)	(5.2M)	(12.8M)
Change in FV of warrant liabilities as % of operating income (loss)	4026%	101%	91%	75%	67%	10%	26%
Net comprehensive income (loss)	(132M)	0.7M)	(2.9M)	(13.6M)	(15.2M)	(44.5M)	(0.035)

Source: Butterfly, SEC

The grandiose domination of the FV of warrant liabilities balance over the income (loss) from operations is very visible in Butterfly's case as the firm, similarly to many SPACs, is struggling to be profitable in the first years after the de-SPAC transaction. What is more important, is the pace at which the balance of warrant liabilities overshadows income (loss):

Figure 9:

Source: Butterfly, SEC

The figure shows the direct inverse correlation between the stock price and the warrant liability account and its grand domination and nullification (in this instance) of any possible net income. It is important to note that the entity only report the liability caused by the *previous* period in the *subsequent* one, which explains the noticeable delay of reaction between stock price increase in 2020 Q4 and warrant liability balance increase in 2020 Q4.

A regression analysis further confirms the negative correlation of stock price and the warrant liability balance:

Figure 10 (excerpt):

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.938766794
R Square	0.881283093
Adjusted R Square	0.857539712
Standard Error	15416935.01
Observations	7

- Significance F: 0.001723948 ← *If significance is ≤ 0.05 it means that data is reliable, the smaller the number, the more reliable.*
- Coefficient: -6624410.71 ← *For every \$1 increase in share price, the FV of warrant liabilities decreases by ~6,624,411 (if the number of common shares outstanding remains constant).*

This observation, though justified in previous parts with the explanation of the warrants' provisions and their respective redemption features (see ***SPAC Warrant Classification Decision*** [p. 40]), is critical to understanding how an increase in the Class A share's value, which is a favorable change, brings unfavorable consequences of increasing the company's liabilities.

Butterfly included a footnote outlining the provision and its redemption features in their Form 10-K for the period ended 12.31.2021 (*the footnote is included in appx. 1, p. 65*).

To summarize, Butterfly will record an approximated contingent liability of the difference between the warrant's strike (\$11.50) and the Class A share's MV.

Conclusion

SPAC warrants need be recorded as liabilities because of their redemption nature dependent on the kind of shareholder and them not being perfectly indexed to the common stock. Through these two characteristics, the warrants meet the liability test under ASC 815. FASB's GAAP is rule based; therefore, the staff opinion is also rule based.

With the knowledge of the nature, computation, and treatment of warrant liabilities, a potential investor may choose to compute benchmarks without including the warrant liability balance and exclude it from the balance sheet to compute a pro forma EPS:

Figure 8:

	Three months ended								
	6/30/2020	9/30/2020	12/31/2020	3/31/2021	6/30/2021	9/30/2021	12/31/2021	3/31/2022	6/30/2022
Income									
(loss) from operations	(0.12M)	(0.46M)	(3.19M)	(53.75M)	(36.69M)	(56.99M)	(45.31M)	(49.53M)	(48.46M)
Warrant liabilities	\$ -	-	-	133.21M	99.74M	56.80M	26.23M	21.07M	8.26M
Change in FV of warrant liabilities	\$ -	-	(128.46M)	(54.11M)	(33.46M)	(42.96M)	(30.57M)	(5.16M)	(12.81M)
Weighted average number of shares outstanding	-	-	9,839,969	105,916,706	192,180,141	196,095,192	173,810,053	199,000,258	199,399,356
EPS (Class A and B, basic and diluted)	\$ -	-	(13.40)	(0.01)	(0.02)	(0.07)	(0.09)	(0.22)	(0.00)
Suggested adjustment	\$ -	-	128.46M	54.11	33.46M	42.96M	30.57M	5.16	12.81
Suggested adjustment per share	-	-	13.05	0.51	0.17	0.22	0.18	0.03	0.06
Pro forma EPS	\$ -	-	(0.34)	0.50	0.16	0.15	0.09	(0.20)	0.06

Though still unprofitable (Butterfly's expenses still exceed its revenues), the pro forma adjustment revealed two consecutive quarters of profit during the post-pandemic boom in the second and third quarters of 2021 and reduced the overall losses per share. Though

warrant liabilities will remain on the balance sheet as a contingency, they must not be fully ignored by the investor. In an unlikely circumstance of a sellout, the company might be required to pay out the liability.

Once (if) the company is able to have all the IPO warrants exercised, the warrant liability account will disappear, and the company's net income and EPS will reflect the pro forma amounts.

To finally answer the research questions:

- Can the statements of a company's financial position be presented in an alternative way as to separate changes in FV of warrant liabilities from net comprehensive income (loss)?

Yes, the investor may choose to compute pro forma net income and EPS. An example is shown in figures 11 and 12.

- Can and should warrant liabilities be excluded from EPS calculation?

No, the warrant liabilities are contingent liabilities according to GAAP and must be accounted for in the computation of EPS.

- If not, how can a company and its regulating bodies better inform investors on how to interpret warrant liabilities?

The company may elect to offer additional explanation (on top of the regulatory footnote and the warrant redemption provisions) and offer guidance on how different events, including but not limited to stock price fluctuations or sellouts, may affect the company's financial position.

Figures

Figure 1:

Warrant liability FV changes demonstration						
	Stock price	Warrant strike price	Warrant FV	Stock price % change	Warrant FV % change	Warrant FV as % of Stock price
At issuance	\$ 10.00	\$ 11.50	\$ -			
Price decrease scenario	\$ 5.00	\$ 11.50	\$ -	-50%	-	-
	15.00	11.50	3.50	200%	-	23%
Price Increase scenarios	20.00	11.50	8.50	33%	143%	43%
	80.00	11.50	68.50	300%	706%	86%
	50.00	11.50	38.50	-38%	-44%	77%
	100.00	11.50	88.50	25%	29%	89%

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

Source: Statista

Figure 4:

Source: Statista

Figure 5:

Source: Ernst & Young, FASB

Figure 6:

BUTTERFLY NETWORK, INC. (f/k/a LONGVIEW ACQUISITION CORP.)
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Loss before provision for income taxes	(132,168,136)
Provision for income taxes	(36,632)
Net loss	\$ (132,204,768)
Weighted average shares outstanding of Class A redeemable common stock	40,948,182.0
Basic and diluted income per share, Class A redeemable common stock	\$ —

Source: Butterfly, SEC

Figure 7:

Reporting entity	Three months ended											
	6/30/2020	9/30/2020	12/31/2020	3/31/2021	6/30/2021	9/30/2021	12/31/2021	3/31/2022	6/30/2022	Longview	Butterfly	Butterfly
Income (loss) from operations	\$ (120,229)	(462,905.00)	(3,190,991.00)	(53,748,000.00)	(36,687,000.00)	(56,987,000.00)	(45,306,000.00)	(49,533,000.00)	(48,455,000.00)			
Warrant liabilities	\$ -	-	-	133,214,000.00	99,754,000.00	56,796,000.00	26,229,000.00	21,066,000.00	8,261,000.00			
Change in FV of warrant liabilities	\$ -	-	(128,463,731.00)	(54,112,000.00)	(33,458,000.00)	(42,958,000.00)	(30,567,000.00)	(5,163,000.00)	(12,805,000.00)			
FV of warrant liabilities as % of operating income (loss)	0%	0%	0%	140%	137%	200%	273%	335%	687%			
Net comprehensive income (loss)	\$ (63,099)	(327,056.00)	(131,814,633.00)	(690,000.00)	(2,942,000.00)	(13,561,000.00)	(15,216,000.00)	(44,477,000.00)	(35,801.00)			
Weighted average number of shares outstanding	0	0	9,839,969	105,916,706	192,180,141	196,095,192	173,810,053	199,000,258	199,399,356			
EPS (Class A and B, basic and diluted)	\$ -	-	(13.40)	(0.01)	(0.02)	(0.07)	(0.09)	(0.22)	(0.00)			
BFLY share price at close	\$ -	9.79	19.65	14.48	10.74	10.32	6.73	3.33	4.34			
Change in price from previous quarter	\$ -	9.79	9.86	(5.17)	(3.74)	(0.42)	(3.59)	(3.40)	1.01			
Change in FV of warrant liabilities	\$ -	-	(128,463,731.00)	(54,112,000.00)	(33,458,000.00)	(42,958,000.00)	(30,567,000.00)	(5,163,000.00)	(12,805,000.00)			
Correlation between change in share price and FV of warrant liabilities												
FV of warrant liabilities regression coefficient of \$6,024,411 per \$1 change in share price.												

Source: Butterfly, SEC

Figure 8:

	Three months ended								
	6/30/2020	9/30/2020	12/31/2020	3/31/2021	6/30/2021	9/30/2021	12/31/2021	3/31/2022	6/30/2022
Income (loss) from operations	(0.12M)	(0.46M)	(3.19M)	(53.75M)	(36.69M)	(56.99M)	(45.31M)	(49.53M)	(48.46M)
Warrant liabilities	\$ -	-	-	133.21M	99.74M	56.80M	26.23M	21.07M	8.26M
Change in FV of warrant liabilities	\$ -	-	(128.46M)	(54.11M)	(33.46M)	(42.96M)	(30.57M)	(5.16M)	(12.81M)
Weighted average number of shares outstanding	-	-	9,839,969	105,916,706	192,180,141	196,095,192	173,810,053	199,000,258	199,399,356
EPS (Class A and B, basic and diluted)	\$ -	-	(13.40)	(0.01)	(0.02)	(0.07)	(0.09)	(0.22)	(0.00)
Suggested adjustment	\$ -	-	128.46M	54.11	33.46M	42.96M	30.57M	5.16	12.81
Suggested adjustment per share	-	-	13.05	0.51	0.17	0.22	0.18	0.03	0.06
Pro forma EPS	\$ -	-	(0.34)	0.50	0.16	0.15	0.09	(0.20)	0.06

Source: Butterfly, SEC

Figure 9:

Source: Butterfly, SEC

Figure 10:

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.938766794
R Square	0.881283093
Adjusted R Square	0.857539712
Standard Error	15416935.01
Observations	7

ANOVA					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	8.82204E+15	8.82204E+15	37.117	0.001723948
Residual	5	1.18841E+15	2.37682E+14		
Total	6	1.00104E+16			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	21923715.75	12280146.62	1.785297556	0.134276	-9643406.09	53490837.6	-9643406.09	53490837.6
BFLY share price	-6624410.71	1087328.611	-6.092372301	0.001724	-9419477.89	-3829343.53	-9419477.886	-3829343.534

Figure 11

Source: Butterfly, SEC

Figure 12

Source: Butterfly, SEC

Appendix

Appx. 1: Butterfly, Inc. Form 10-K for the period ended 12.31.2021. Footnote describing the public warrants' provisions and redemption features.

At any time while the warrants are exercisable, the Company may redeem not less than all of the outstanding Public Warrants:

- at a price of \$0.01 per warrant;
- upon a minimum of 30 days' prior written notice of redemption (the "30-day redemption period") to each warrant holder;
- provided that the last reported sale price of the Class A common stock equals or exceeds \$18.00 per share (as adjusted for stock splits, stock dividends, reorganizations, recapitalizations and the like and for certain issuances of Class A common stock and equity-linked securities) for any 20 trading days within a 30-trading day period ending on the third trading day prior to the date the Company sends the notice of redemption to the warrant holders; and
- provided that there is an effective registration statement covering the issuance of the shares of Class A common stock issuable upon exercise of the warrants, and a current prospectus relating thereto, available through the 30-day redemption period or the Company has elected to require the exercise of the warrants on a "cashless basis" (as described below).

If the foregoing conditions are satisfied and the Company issues a notice of redemption of the Public Warrants at \$0.01 per warrant, each holder of Public Warrants will be entitled to exercise his, her or its Public Warrants prior to the scheduled redemption date.

If the Company calls the Public Warrants for redemption for \$0.01 as described above, the Board may elect to require any holder that wishes to exercise his, her or its Public Warrant to do so on a “cashless basis.” If the Board makes such election, all holders of Public Warrants would pay the exercise price by surrendering their warrants for that number of shares of Class A common stock equal to the quotient obtained by dividing (x) the product of the number of shares of Class A common stock underlying the warrants, multiplied by the excess of the “fair market value” over the exercise price of the warrants by (y) the “fair market value.” For purposes of the redemption provisions of the warrants, the “fair market value” means the average last reported sale price of the Class A common stock for the 10 trading days ending on the third trading day prior to the date on which the notice of redemption is sent to the holders of warrants.

Commencing 90 days after the warrants become exercisable, the Company may redeem not less than all of the outstanding Public Warrants and Private Warrants:

- at \$0.10 per warrant;
- upon a minimum of 30 days’ prior written notice of redemption;
- provided that the last reported sale price of the Class A common stock equals or exceeds \$10.00 per share (as adjusted per stock splits, stock dividends, reorganizations, reclassifications, recapitalizations and the like) on the trading day

- prior to the date on which the Company sends the notice of redemption to the warrant holders;
- provided that the Private Warrants are also concurrently exchanged at the same price (equal to a number of shares of Class A common stock) as the outstanding Public Warrants; and
 - provided that there is an effective registration statement covering the issuance of the shares of Class A common stock issuable upon exercise of the warrants and a current prospectus relating thereto available throughout the 30-day redemption period.

If the foregoing conditions are satisfied and the Company issues a notice of redemption of the warrants at \$0.10 per warrant, each warrant holder will be entitled to exercise his, her or its warrant prior to the scheduled redemption date on a cashless basis and receive that number of shares based on the redemption date and the “fair market value” of the Class A common stock, in accordance with a table set forth in the warrant agreement.

The Company evaluated the Public Warrants under ASC 815-40, Derivatives and Hedging—Contracts in Entity’s Own Equity, in conjunction with the SEC Division of Corporation Finance’s April 12, 2021 Public Statement, Staff Statement on Accounting and Reporting Considerations for Warrants Issued by Special Purpose Acquisition Companies (“SPACs”), and concluded that they do not meet the criteria to be classified in stockholders’ equity. Specifically, the exercise of the warrants may be settled in cash upon the occurrence of a tender offer or exchange offer in which the maker of the tender offer or exchange offer, upon completion of the tender offer or exchange offer,

beneficially owns more than 50% of the outstanding shares of the Company's Class A common stock, even if it would not result in a change of control of the Company. This provision would preclude the warrants from being classified in equity and thus the warrants should be classified as a liability.

Source: Butterfly, SEC

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